

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ABILITY IN CREATING AND IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIONS FOR THE SUCCESS OF LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE ORGANIZATIONS IN SAMUT PRAKAN PROVINCE

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Abstract

Local government organizations are ones of the important mechanisms for driving the country's development in accordance with the policy guidelines and directions set forth in the framework of state administration in order to achieve the vision of "Thailand is stable, prosperous, and sustainable". However, the bureaucratic system has a large organizational structure and a centralized chain of command, causing delays and inefficiencies to the extent that it cannot meet the needs of people. Based on the problems and obstacles of the bureaucratic system, the idea of adopting a new government management approach to reform the Thai bureaucratic system by using effective innovative management tools of the executives has occurred. The objectives of this research were to: 1) study levels of environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources, and the ability to create and implement innovations for the success; 2) examine influences of environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources on the ability to create and implement innovations for the success; and 3) develop a model of the ability to create and implement innovations for the success. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining quantitative and qualitative methods. For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 300 executives of local administrative organizations in SamutPrakan Province. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. They were selected via stratified sampling. Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with a structural equation model. As for the qualitative research component, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants consisting of executives and experts in local government organizations in SamutPrakan Province. The findings showed that: 1) environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources, and the ability to create and implement innovations for the success were rated at a high level; 2) environment, management competency, knowledge management, and enterprise resources had an influence on the ability to create and implement innovations for the success, with a .05 level of statistical significance; and 3) the model of the ability to create and implement innovations for the success, developed by the researcher, was called 2EKCAS Model, consisting of E (referring to enterprise resources), E (referring to environment), K (referring to knowledge management), C (referring to management competency), and AS (referring to ability to create and implement innovations for the success). These findings can be used to develop cooperation between organizations in the public and private sectors in various forms in order to serve people and create public benefits in the areas which in turn help the local government organizations to provide public service effectively. These actions will positively affect the quality of life of people in the area.

Keywords: Factors/ Innovation Competency of Executives/ Local Administrative Organizations/ Samut Prakan Province

1. Introduction

Local government organizations are one of the important mechanisms for driving the country's development in accordance with the policy guidelines and directions set forth in the framework of state administration in order to achieve the vision of "Thailand is stable, prosperous, and sustainable". These organizations have influence to promote sustainability at local and national level (Vongsiriwan, 2022). However, the bureaucratic system has a large organizational structure and a centralized chain of command, causing delays and inefficiencies to the extent that it cannot meet the needs of people. Based on the problems and obstacles of the bureaucratic system, the idea of adopting a new government management approach to reform the Thai bureaucratic system by using effective innovative management tools of the executives has occurred.

There are number of issues existing among the local administrative organizations in Thailand (Chatchawan, Trichandhara, & Rinthaisong, 2017). These organizations are based on government rules and regulations and the operations of these organizations are conducting by the government officials. Furthermore, the poor performance of these organizations is found among various provinces of Thailand. These organizations could not get success in different operations and the implementation of rules and regulations. As local government organizations are the responsible for implementation of various rules and regulations (Julnes & Holzer, 2001) for the welfare of the society and lead towards the transparency and accountability. However, these organizations have not achieved the satisfactory level in these operations. The lower performance of the organizations causes several issues practically among the societies. Facing the troubles due to the inefficient management of these government organizations. No doubt these organizations are working in various parts of Thailand and achieved various objectives which lead towards the welfare of the people, but still the performance of these organizations is needed to improve.

Most importantly the Samut Prakan Province of Thailand is facing different challenges related to the local administrative organizations. Samut Prakan, a central Thai province on the Gulf of Thailand, sits just south of Bangkok at the mouth of the Chao Phraya River (Suanmali, Kokuenkan, Lohananthachai, Kumpong, & Suwatanapornchai, 2018). The rea of Samut Prakan Province is 1,004 km² with 1.345 million populations. Local government organizations are existing in Samut Prakan Province and performing their operations. These organizations have achieved several important goals and increases the level of performance, but several challenges exist among the societies. It is needed to address by these organizations. The satisfactory level of success among various operations by these organizations is not achieved in Samut Prakan Province. The ineffective implementation of various policies causes to decrease in the level of success in several objectives.

These problems can be achieved with the help of different ways. The better implementation of various strategies can increase the success level among local government organizations. According to the current study, the environment (Stefanović, Urošević, & Mladenović-Ranisavljević, 2018) among these organization is needed to improve. The better environment among these organizations can lead to the success with the help of management competencies,

knowledge management and resources. The available of resources must be ensured along with the proper management competencies and knowledge management. Environment management and resources can play role in the success of local administrative organizations in Samut Prakan Province. Finally, the objectives of this research include; 1) study levels of environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources, and the ability to create and implement innovations for the success; 2) examine influences of environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources on the ability to create and implement innovations for the success; and 3) develop a model of the ability to create and implement innovations for the success.

Several studies carried out on local government organizations (Drogalas, Petridis, Petridis, & Zografidou, 2020; Praditsil, Saensanoh, & Archeewa, 2022), however, these studies have not covered the important elements which are covered by the current study. Previous studies addressed different dimensions of these organizations along with different factors; however the role of environment is not addressed by preceding study. Therefore, they study has major significance for the literature because different theoretical problems are covered in the study. Furthermore, by contributing theoretically, this study has major significance because the current study addressed the role of management competencies among the government organizations. At the local level, the public organizations are lacking in various competencies which are required to perform efficiently. This problem is not addressed by the other studies in literature. Furthermore, this study addressed several important aspects of knowledge management and enterprise resources among the public administrative organizations in Thailand. Therefore, this study has major significance for the practices and theory in relation to the local administrative organizations in Thailand.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Local Administrative Organizations Success

This study dealing with the local administrative organizations related to the government of Thailand. There are 75 local administrations working in various provinces of Thailand. The 75 local administrative organization has central importance in all provinces due to various significant operations. The operations of the administrative organizations have valuable benefits for the society and it has significant effect on the development of society through various dimensions. As reported in the literature local administrative organizations has playing most critical role in any society (Chatchawan et al., 2017; Vongsiriwan, 2022). Generally, it is based on the good governance practices which follow the different principles. The most important principle of local administrative organizations is the role in law implementation. These organizations focus (Chatchawan et al., 2017; Praditsil et al., 2022) on various rules, regulations, ordinance as well as notification in line with the society and try to implement rules and regulations in the favor of the public. The law-and-order situation in any nation has significant role for the development. Similarly, the rule of law in Thailand is important in all provinces which is based on the good governance of local administrative organization. Furthermore, morality as well as ethics are also connected with the administrative organization.

These organizations have important role in capacity building programs to promote honesty, sincerity, diligence and patience along with various valuable practices related to the morality or ethics. All these elements have critical role for the development of a society. Furthermore, any other important element of local administrative organizations is transparency. The promotion of maximum transparency in the work is most important for any nation because it led to decrease in conflicts. The trust on the nation is important to build with the help of good governance of administrative organizations. And other important element of good governance of local administrative organizations is participation of people in a society in various matters is based on the effective operations of administrative organization which lead to the valuable decision making. Good governance of the local administrative organizations is also based on the accountability. The government organizations in various provinces must ensure the actions with proper accountability. The accountability must be continued in all the decision making and to solve various problems on timely basis in the society. In addition to this, the action taken by these organizations in any society must be accepted with the consequences which also the most important element of these organizations. The responsibility of these organization is to maximize limited resources and increase the capacity as well as effectiveness. Therefore, local administrative bodies are most important to play role in the society, particularly in the Thailand these organizations have most important role (Praditsil et al., 2022). And these organizations are involved in various valuable practices such as rule of law, morality, transparency participation, accountability as well as efficiency.

2.2 Environment

There are number of factors affecting the organizations along with the different operations performed in the organization to achieve the objectives (Rouibah, Dihani, & Al-Qirim, 2020). The environment of the any organization has major contribution towards the success as well as failure of the organization in specific tasks. A positive environment among the organizations always leads towards better development of all the operations, however negative environment may lead to the failure of the operations. Therefore, the availability of suitable environment at workplace is most important to perform better. The employees working in any organization requires supportive environment to complete various activities. It has direct effect on the performance of various activities by the organizations. It is reported in previous studies that environment of the organization has effect on the overall performance (Mahrous & Genedy, 2018). Similarly, the environment of the organization has effect on the local administrative operations. The local administrative organizations working in any area required better environment for the individuals to perform different actions. Similar with the other organizations, the environment of administrative organizations has influence on the success. As reported by prior studies that environment has major contribution to the rate of success. Environment of the organizations have influence on the success of local administrative organizations. The level of success by the local administrative organizations can be determined with the help of working environment among these organizations. Therefore, this study attempted to examine the direct effect of environment on the success of local administrative organizations.

Hypothesis 1: Environment has positive effect on success.

2.3 Management competency

To perform better operations among the organizations, the role of human resources is most important (Zhao & Huang, 2022). All the operations in any organization depends upon the human resources. Similarly, the rate of success as well as higher performance can be achieved with the help of better human resources. These resources include skills as well as capabilities of the employees. Better skills and capabilities of the employees denotes to the competencies. A competency to perform a specific operation is one of the basic elements to get success. Along with the competencies of the employees, the competencies of the management have key importance. Because the management lead the employees towards the achievement of various objectives. Furthermore, competencies in management may lead to decrease in the rate of success. As it is reported in previous studies that competencies are the mandatory element of success (Iskandar & Kaltum, 2022). The management competencies are based on the unique skills that improve the efficiency as well as performance. Satisfactory level of efficiency achievement is mandatory for the organizations to get success in different operations. Therefore, competitive employees among the organizations are most important. Similar with the other organizations, the role of competencies is also important among the local organizations. The operations of local administrative organizations can be performed with the help of better competencies. Hence, this study proposed the effect of management competencies on success. Furthermore, the management competencies are also influenced by the employees of the organization. A better environment in the organization lead to the significant effect on management competencies. Competencies are only helpful for the organization if the employees use their competencies to perform various task and continue towards the growth. In this way the employees require supportive environment in the organization. The support from the management can create a better environment to use the skills as well as capabilities for the betterment of the organization. Therefore, environment also has effect on management competencies.

Hypothesis 2: Management competitive has positive effect on success.

Hypothesis 3: Environment has positive effect on management competencies.

2.4 Knowledge management

Knowledge management (KM) is the process of organizing, creating, using, and sharing collective knowledge within an organization. Successful knowledge management includes maintaining information in a place where it is easy to access. Knowledge is one of the vital assets for the organizations to perform better in various operations (Chatzoudes, Chatzoglou, & Vraimaki, 2015). The knowledge of the employees working in the organizations can be helpful to convert various ideas into innovation. Similarly, the knowledge management may have role in the local administrative institutions. The knowledge management is majorly based on the organizational information, usage of information and sharing of knowledge within the organization. The maintenance of information on a suitable place is most important for the organization to access and generate new ideas. The role of knowledge management among the

local administrative organizations is most important to handle various operations with the help of valuable ideas. It is an important element and it has significant effect on organizations(Hussein, 2022). The knowledge management has influence on the resources of the company as knowledge is the resource of the company which can lead the company towards achievement of better level in resources utilization.

Hypothesis 4: Knowledge management has positive effect on success.

Hypothesis 5: Knowledge management has positive effect on resources.

Hypothesis 6: Management competitive has positive effect on knowledge management.

2.5 Enterprise Resources

There are several types of resources among the organizations and all the resources has important role in the success of organization(C.-J. Chen, Guo, Hsiao, & Hu, 2018). The most important types of resources are the tangible resources as well as intangible resources. Tangible resources include the assets of the company on the other hand intangible assets include various skills of the company. All the types of resources have major effect on the overall performance of the employees(Xu, Huo, & Sun, 2014). According to the resource-based view (RBV), the success of any business is dependent on the resources. The better availability of resources ensured the success of the company in any business activity;however, the less availability of resources lead to the dissatisfaction of the people. Therefore, resources are the key elements among the organizations. The environment of the company also influences the resources. A better relationship between environment and resources may lead to the success. As reported in previous studies that environment and resources have relationship with each other. The availability of better environment for the employees may lead to the achievement of higher performance through success. Therefore, environment has direct effect on resources and success.

Hypothesis 7: Environment has positive effect on resources.

Hypothesis 8: Resources has positive effect on success.

Hypothesis 9: Management competitive has positive effect on resources.

Moreover, along with the direct effect, the current study also considered different indirect effects. The indirect effects are purposed based on management competency, knowledge management and resources. The indirect effect of management competency is considered between environment and knowledge management. (Kerdpitak et al., 2022)The mediation effect of management competencies is considered between environment and resources. Furthermore, the mediation effect of knowledge management is considered between environment and management competencies. Additionally, the mediation effect of resources is considered between environment and success. The mediation effect of resources is considered knowledge management and success. Finally, the mediates effect of resources is considered between management competencies and success.

Hypothesis 10: Management competencies mediates the relationship between environment and knowledge management.

Hypothesis 11: Management competencies mediates the relationship between environment and resources.

Hypothesis 12: Knowledge management mediates the relationship between environment and management competencies.

Hypothesis 13: Resources mediates the relationship between environment and success.

Hypothesis 14: Resources mediates the relationship between knowledge management and success.

Hypothesis 15: Resources mediates the relationship between management competencies and success.

3. Research Methodology

Appropriate methodology selection to conduct a research study is most critical. Therefore, by considering the relationship considered in this study, a mixed research methodology combining quantitative and qualitative methods is employed. The mixed methodology has valuable importance for the study because both the results obtained from the quantitative approach is confirmed with the help of qualitative approach. Furthermore, this study used qualitative research approach for deep understanding of the relationship discussed in this study.

For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 300 executives of local administrative organizations in SamutPrakan Province. The questionnaires are developed by considering the measures already revealed in previous studies. After the development of questionnaire, it is distributed among the local administrative organizations working in SamutPrakan Province of Thailand. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. Respondents were selected via stratified sampling which is most suitable in the current study. Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with structural equation model. As for the qualitative research part, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants consisting of executives and experts in local government organizations in SamutPrakan Province. Finally, the data statistics are presented in Table 1 in which the standard deviation, mean, normality of the data and significance value (p-value) is highlighted.

Table 1: Statistical test of empirical variables (n=300)

Variable	M	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
chll	3.97	1.00	25.19	-2.438	-2.419	11.796	.003
inno	3.93	1.08	27.48	-2.375	-2.571	12.246	.002
visi	4.25	.71	16.71	-2.749	-1.253	9.126	.010
lead	3.85	1.22	31.69	-2.252	-4.938	29.456	.000
stra	4.23	.78	18.44	-3.170	-1.822	13.371	.001
assi	4.25	.75	17.65	-2.709	-1.240	8.879	.012
sepe	4.19	.76	18.14	-2.652	-1.290	8.700	.013
orim	4.27	.78	18.27	-3.397	-1.939	15.297	.000
depa	4.28	.69	16.12	-2.659	-1.191	8.490	.014
hrm	4.21	.75	17.81	-2.700	-1.083	8.460	.015
fina	4.23	.72	17.02	-2.668	-1.216	8.597	.014
mate	4.23	.77	18.20	-3.070	-1.882	12.968	.002
perf	3.71	1.23	33.15	-1.361	-3.513	14.192	.001
conf	3.62	1.23	33.98	-1.076	-4.725	23.486	.000
acce	4.28	.66	15.42	-2.545	-1.748	9.531	.009

4. Results

There are a number of data analysis techniques available in the literature however the suitable data analysis technique selection is most important because the results of the study are majorly based on the data analysis technique. Therefore, by considering the valuable suggestions of literature as well as by considering the nature of the study, this study selected structural equation modeling (SEM) which is most prominent and suitable data analysis techniques in the current study (Hair Jr et al., 2021; Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Therefore, this study employed SEM technique to analyze the structural relationship between the variables. In first part of the analysis, the current study examined reliability through Cronbach alpha and by considering factor loadings. Cronbach alpha must be higher than 0.7 and factor loadings must be higher than 0.4. Different studies consider different levels of factor loading but this study considered 0.4 as minimum level to retain the items. The factor loading is shown in Figure 1 and all the results are given in Table 2. It is found that all the variables have Cronbach alpha is above 0.7 and sector loading higher than 0.4. Furthermore, this study also considered the convergent validity and discriminant validity and found that the data is accurate to proceed for further analysis.

Figure 1: Model (n=300)

Note: Environment=ENVIR; Management competency= COMPE; Knowledge management = KNOMA; Enterprise resources = RESOU; Success = SUCCE

Table 2: Factor Loadings. (n = 300)

Variable	Factor Loading(λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
Environment(ENVIR)				
Chll	0.98	0.05	23.25	0.95
inno	0.71	0.5	13.94	0.5
$\rho_{\chi}48. = \rho_{\omega} = 27.$				
Management competency(COMPE)				
visi	0.78	0.4	12.26	0.6
lead	0.58	0.46	9.58	0.54
stra	0.61	0.43	9.27	0.57
assi	0.72	0.39	11.25	0.61
$\rho_{\chi}18. = \rho_{\omega} = 25.$				
Knowledge management(KNOMA)				
sepe	0.82	0.33	15.28	0.67
orim	0.73	0.47	13.42	0.53
depa	0.81	0.34	15.12	0.66
$\rho_{\chi}38. = \rho_{\omega} = 26.$				
Enterprise resources (RESOU)				
hrm	0.82	0.39	14.56	0.61
fina	0.73	0.38	14.68	0.62
mate	0.81	0.36	14.97	0.64
$\rho_{\chi}38. = \rho_{\omega} = 26.$				
Success(SUCCE)				
perf	0.79	0.38	12	0.62
Conf	0.87	0.24	12.96	0.76
acce	0.44	0.8	7.36	0.2
$\rho_{\chi}67. = \rho_{\omega} = 25.$				

Note: Environment=ENVIR; Management competency= COMPE; Knowledge management = KNOMA; Enterprise resources = RESOU; Success = SUCCE

To test the relationship between constructs, this study employed SEM structural model by using AMOS (Mustafa, Nordin, & Razzaq, 2020; Purwanto, Asbari, Santoso, Paramarta, & Sunarsi, 2020; Rahi & Abd Ghani, 2018). Results of the hypothesis are given in Table 3. T-value 1.96 and beta value is considered to test the variables. The results show that environment has significant relationship with success of local administrative organizations in Thailand. Management competency is also having significant effect on success. Therefore, these hypotheses 1, hypothesis 2 and hypothesis 3 are supported by the results of the study. Furthermore, it is evident that environment has positive effect on management competencies. Besides, knowledge management has significant effect on success and resources of the organizations. Additionally, the positive effect of management competences is found in relation to the knowledge management. In addition, environment also found positively correlated with resources and resources found positively correlated with success of the local administrative organizations. Furthermore, it is found that management competences have significant relationship with the resources. The results supported hypothesis 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. Finally, this study addressed the indirect effect of management competency, knowledge management, and resources between environment and success.

Table 3: Parameter estimation result of direct effect coefficient, indirect effect, and total effect from adjusting model (n=300)

Variable	R ²	Effect	Variable			
			COMPE	KNOMA	RESOU	ENVIR
COMPE	.49	DE	-	-	-	.70*(10.16)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	-	-	.70*(10.16)
KNOMA	.92	DE	.96*(12.53)	-	-	-
		IE	-	-	-	.67(10.86)
		TE	.96*(12.53)	-	-	.67(10.86)
RESOU	.92	DE	.48*(4.27)	.73*(6.07)	-	.46*(6.40)
		IE	.33*(4.07)	-	-	.30*(9.34)
		TE	.81*(11.84)	.73*(6.07)	-	.76*(9.63)
SUCCE	.90	DE	.46*(6.92)	.49*(7.76)	.77*(8.17)	.73*(6.39)
		IE	.24*(6.10)	.32*(7.07)	-	.18*(4.74)
		TE	.79*(6.79)	.81*(8.97)	.77*(8.17)	.91*(11.19)

$\chi^2 = 113.83$ df = 69 p-value = .00055, $\chi^2 / df = 1.64$, RMSEA = .047, RMR = .027, SRMR = .036, CFI = .95, GFI = .92, AGFI = .90, CN = 262.91

Note: Environment=ENVIR; Management competency= COMPE; Knowledge management = KNOMA; Enterprise resources = RESOU; Success = SUCCE

Results indicated that management competencies are a mediating variable between environment and knowledge management. It is also found that management competences are mediating variable between environment and resources which is statistically significant. Similarly, knowledge management found to be a mediating variable between environment and management competences. It is also found that the mediation effect of resources between environment and success, knowledge management and success is statistically significant. Finally, the resources are also a mediating variable between management competences and

success. Therefore, the mediating hypothesis 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 are statistically significant.

5. Discussion

The hypothesis of the study revealed important results in relation to the local administrative organizations. The relationship between environment and success is significant and positive shows that environment of the organization can increase the level of success. Therefore, a positive environment among the local administrative organizations can increase the success among various operations in Thailand. These results are also supported with the help of previous studies which shows the positive relationship between environment and success Hayat, Shakeel, and Chen (2021). Furthermore, the relationship between management competencies and success is also considered. Similar with the environment, management competencies have positive effect on success which shows that increase in the level of management competency can increase the success. As management competencies are connected with the human resources, therefore, the availability of human resources is important to achieve success. Literature also demonstrated the positive relationship between management competencies and success (T. Chen et al., 2019). Furthermore, this study examined the effect of environment on management competencies. The environment of the organizations found positively correlated with management competencies which indicated that supportive environment among the organizations lead to the management competencies. The benefits from the skills of the employees can be achieved with the help of providing supportive as well as friendly environment at workplace. Furthermore, a positive effect of knowledge management is found on enterprise success. The collection of information from resources also causes to achieve success because this study found that increase in knowledge management among the organizations can increase the possibility of success. Similarly, literature addressed the positive relationship between knowledge management and success (Heisig et al., 2016). Moreover, the relationship between environment and resources is considered. Results shows that supportive environment create the resources for the organization. As the positive effect between environment and resources is found in the study. Nevertheless, resources found positively correlated with success which shows that the increase in the resources of the organization increases the success. Therefore, it is in line with the guidelines of resource-based view (Nair & Bhattacharyya, 2019). Similar with the resource-based view, this study found that resources have vital importance in success.

The current study examined the indirect effect of management competencies, knowledge management and enterprise resources. It is found that management competencies can transfer the positive effect of environment on knowledge management. It is also found that management competencies can transfer the positive effect of environment on resources. Similarly, the results of indirect effect highlighted that knowledge management can transfer the positive effect of environment on management competencies. Furthermore, resources can transfer the positive effect of environment and knowledge management on success of local administrative organizations in Thailand. Finally, it is evident from the results that resources have the potential

to transfer the positive effect of management competency on success among the local administrative organizations in Thailand.

6. Conclusion

This study found that environment has influential role to enhance success of local administrative organizations. Along with the environment, the role of management competency, knowledge management and enterprise resources have key importance to achieve success. The findings showed that: 1) environment, management competency, knowledge management, enterprise resources, and the ability to create and implement innovations for the success were rated at a high level; 2) environment, management competency, knowledge management, and enterprise resources has influence on the ability to create and implement innovations for the success, and 3) the model of the ability to create and implement innovations for the success, developed by this study is called EEKCAS Model, consisting of E (referring to enterprise resources), E (referring to environment), K (referring to knowledge management), C (referring to management competency), and AS (referring to ability to create and implement innovations for the success).

6.1 Implications

This study has valuable theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically the study contributed by considering the relationship between environment, management competencies, knowledge management, resources and success of local administrative organizations in Thailand. This is the most important relationship which is not highlighted among the previous studies in relation to the local administrative organizations in Thailand. This is the pioneer study which considered various newly developed direct as well as indirect effects. Indirect effect the study considered the role of environment on management competencies, knowledge management and resources. These relationships are rarely addressed in previous studies. The relationship considered by the current study between environment and success is also less discussed in the literature. Furthermore, this study considered the mediation effect of management competencies, knowledge management and resources between environment and success which is not highlighted in previous studies. Similarly, while contributing contextually, the current study contributed by considering SamutPrakan Province of Thailand which is not considered in other studies.

Furthermore, this study also has important practical implications because this study considered important aspects of the literature which were not covered in previous investigations. As the current study addressed that the role of environment is key to get success by the local administrative organization in Thailand, therefore, the management of these organizations should promote supportive working environment. Similarly, the current study recommended that the management of these organizations should consider human resources on priority and the skills of employees must be encouraged. Similarly, the management of these organizations should enhance knowledge management capability of the employees. Finally, this study recommended that the management of the organizations should focus on to gain better resources to make the operation successful. These findings can be used to develop cooperation

between organizations in the public and private sectors in various forms in order to serve people and create public benefits in the areas which in turn help the local government organizations to provide public service effectively. These actions will positively affect the quality of life of people in the area.

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